

Silent Signals, Loud Threats: Using dApps for Radio Signal Intelligence-based Intrusion Detection in 5G O-RAN

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Abstract—As 5G networks evolve toward disaggregated Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architectures, low-latency, edge-resident security mechanisms are critical. Conventional Extended Application (xApp)-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) at the Central Unit (CU) create high computational overhead and latency due to their reliance on deep packet inspection and centralized analytics. This work proposes a lightweight, Distributed Application (dApp)-based IDS deployed at the Distributed Unit (DU) for near-real-time threat detection at the radio edge. Our approach leverages radio telemetry features from the E2 interface to identify network attacks without inspecting upper-layer packet data. Using a live 5G O-RAN testbed, we constructed synchronized datasets from the DU (lower-layer) and CU (upper-layer) under various attack scenarios to evaluate several Machine Learning (ML) models. The results demonstrate that our dApp-based IDS achieves comparable accuracy to traditional xApp systems while significantly reducing CPU effort, memory usage, and execution time, underscoring the potential of dApps as scalable and effective security primitives in O-RAN.

Index Terms—O-RAN, dApps, RAN Data, ML, IDS

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of mobile communication networks towards fifth-generation (5G) architectures has ushered in unprecedented demands for scalability, flexibility, and programmability. To facilitate the openness of the network infrastructure, O-RAN is emerging in popularity recently, fulfilling the 5G network demands by disaggregating traditional monolithic base-station functions into a hierarchy of logical entities: the CU, DU, and Radio Unit (RU) [1]. This functional separation, together with open and standardized interfaces, empowers operators to introduce vendor-neutral components. With the flexibility and additional capacity, O-RAN facilitates Artificial Intelligence (AI) at network edges [2], [3], especially providing flexible computing resources on demand for AI operations and customizable distributed network deployments to diverse service requirements.

However, the very features that make 5G O-RAN architectures attractive also create novel security challenges. In conventional O-RAN deployments, a vast majority of security

monitoring and intrusion detection tend to focus on higher-layer traffic within the network, where deep packet inspection (DPI) and application-layer analytics occur. Currently, O-RAN IDS systems are deployed, as xApps at the Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (RT RIC) or as rApps at Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) with Non-RT RIC [4], [5]. DPI may also create privacy and trust issues for end clients. Such centralization can incur substantial backhaul overhead, impose stringent latency and computational demands on the network, and delay the identification of malicious User Equipment (UE) emitting anomalous or attack traffic.

Due to a large amount of data coming to intrusion detection-based xApps and RAN Intelligent Controller Applications (rApps) from many UEs, some of the critical network threats may go unrecognized. Furthermore, late detection at the Near-RT RIC or SMO limits an operator’s ability to isolate or quarantine offender UEs close to the radio edge before they propagate attacks deeper into the network. Also, attackers can harm low-layer devices like CD/DU, which can not be detected with higher-layer traffic [6].

In this work, we propose shifting intrusion detection capabilities closer to the RAN edge by deploying O-RAN dApps [7] directly at the DU, rather than relying solely on centralized detection mechanisms at the RIC or CU to analyze RAN-level radio-signal characteristics in real-time. By capturing radio telemetry—such as Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR), phase response, and modulation quality—directly at the DU, our approach enables early identification and classification of anomalous behavior without relying solely on higher-layer traffic inspection. This DU-centric approach reduces the workload on the CU, Near-RT RIC, and SMO, allowing those components to focus on broader coordination and optimization tasks. Thus enabling rapid, proximity-based response strategies to isolate compromised UEs and protect intermediate network infrastructure. We name our dApp-based platform **RIDGE**: Radio-Informed Distributed Guardian for Edges. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, this is the first attempt to migrate intrusion detection against multiple network attack scenarios with dApps in O-RAN and compare it with conventional xApps.

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Using a custom 5G O-RAN testbed, we generate a realistic dataset by orchestrating multiple UEs under both benign and diverse attack scenarios (e.g., DoS floods, port scans, stealth probes). An O-RAN dApp at the DU captures radio telemetry features, which are processed by lightweight ML models for real-time threat detection. Moreover, this paper will experimentally evaluate whether radio-signal fingerprints alone can effectively distinguish attack types from benign traffic. By enabling edge-level detection at the DU, our approach improves threat response timeliness and granularity, allowing early mitigation of malicious UEs near the RU and enhancing 5G O-RAN resilience.

A. Our Contributions

We summarize our main contributions as follows:

- **Edge-Level IDS with dApps.** We propose deploying IDS within O-RAN dApps at the Distributed Unit (DU) for low-latency, edge-based threat detection.
- **Telemetry-driven mitigation.** Leveraging E2 telemetry, our system detects and mitigates threats early at the DU without relying on packet inspection.
- **Lightweight edge models.** We develop compact ML classifiers tailored for resource-limited DU environments using a minimal yet informative feature set.
- **Real-world testbed deployment.** Our solution is implemented on a live 5G O-RAN testbed with real UEs, evaluating both benign and attack scenarios.
- **Dual dataset creation.** We build two aligned datasets—DU telemetry and CU network traffic—to support comprehensive O-RAN IDS analysis.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses related work, Section III presents our proposed RIDGE dApp and xApp-based architecture, Section IV details of the implementation and dataset collection in our platform, Section V reports a discussion on the experimental findings, and Section VI concludes with future directions.

II. RELATED WORKS

This section discusses the related research works based on IDS, xApps and dApps. We also highlight the research gap identified.

A. IDS Systems for Network Threat Detection

There are recent research focused on developing ML-based IDS using widely available benchmark datasets such as 5G-NIDD, NSL-KDD, CICIDS2017, UNSW-NB15, and BoT-IoT [8]–[11]. However, the vast majority of this research is not focused on O-RAN or even xApp-based implementations. Moreover, they do not focus on radio telemetry, but use DPI-based information. For instance, recent studies have employed classifiers like Least Squares Support Vector Machines (LS-SVM) [8], and ensemble learning techniques [12] to achieve high detection accuracy across these existing datasets. Another work has explored Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to model complex traffic behaviors in IoT environments [9]. While these efforts significantly advance the field of IDS research, they

predominantly assume centralized processing with full packet-level visibility and stable network conditions. Crucially, none of these solutions address the unique architectural challenges of disaggregated and decentralized O-RAN systems, where RAN-layer telemetry and real-time constraints must be considered. Moreover, these IDS frameworks have not been implemented or validated in practical O-RAN deployments, either as xApps or dApps, further highlighting the need for dedicated O-RAN-specific intrusion detection research.

B. xApps for IDS Applications

Recent advancements in O-RAN security have already introduced AI-driven xApps for intrusion detection, primarily operating within the Near-RT RIC. Notable implementations include 5G-SPECTOR [13], which employs a rule-based expert system to detect Layer 3 cellular attacks using E2 telemetry data. It does not use AI or ML-based implementation and only provides an xApp. Similarly, the ZTRAN framework in [14] integrates intrusion detection with secure slicing, leveraging behavior profiling based on Key Performance Measurements (KPMs). However, ZTRAN’s zero-trust architecture on xApps may delay threat detection, allowing malicious activities to propagate deeper into the network.

C. dApps-based Network Applications

dApps represent a promising yet underexplored avenue for enhancing O-RAN security. Operating directly at the DU, dApps can access fine-grained, real-time data, enabling more immediate and localized threat detection and response. Despite their potential, research on dApps, particularly for IDS purposes, remains limited. Current studies have primarily focused on dApp applications for other applications like spectrum sharing and positioning [15], leaving a gap in the exploration of their capabilities for intrusion detection. By leveraging dApps for IDS, it is possible to achieve faster threat detection, reduce the risk of attack propagation, and alleviate the computational burden on centralized network components. This approach aligns with the need for more agile and responsive security mechanisms in the evolving landscape of 5G and beyond. Therefore, this research further investigates the applicability of dApp-enabled IDS for the O-RAN. Table I provides a summary of our work compared to key related contributions.

TABLE I: Comparison of related IDS systems and our proposed dApp-based solution

Feature	[8]	[12]	[14]	[13]	Ours
O-RAN Specific Deployment	–	–	✓	✓	✓
Runs at DU (Edge) via dApps	–	–	–	–	✓
Uses Radio Telemetry (E2 data)	–	–	✓	✓	✓
ML Based Detection	✓	✓	✓	–	✓
Lightweight Deployment	–	–	–	–	✓
Intrusion Detection Functionality	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Support for Real-Time Execution	–	–	–	–	✓
Validated on Real O-RAN	–	–	–	–	✓

III. RIDGE: RADIO-INFORMED DISTRIBUTED GUARDIAN FOR EDGES ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1: The RIDGE architecture with a DU dApp for edge-level radio telemetry and an xApp for network-level monitoring.

The proposed architecture introduces a ML-based IDS for O-RAN, leveraging dApps for edge-level intelligence and xApps for network-wide awareness. As shown in Figure 1, the Near-RT RIC hosts the IDS xApp for RAN-level monitoring via the E2 interface, while the DU hosts dApps for local anomaly detection over the Open Fronthaul, with the SMO providing orchestration support. The figure also highlights the directional flow of telemetry, model updates from the O-Cloud, and interactions between dApps and xApps.

At the edge, the DU telemetry is collected by a monitoring dApp and sent to the O-Cloud—emulated via an edge server—where the training module updates the IDS model. Once trained, optimized inference instances are deployed back as an IDS dApp in the DU, enabling real-time anomaly detection with sub-10 ms latency using the same telemetry inputs. Upon detecting suspicious activity, the system can take immediate action (e.g., flagging or isolating devices) and optionally report to the cloud for continuous learning.

Complementing this edge-based detection, a monitoring xApp is deployed in the Near-RT RIC to monitor network-level indicators across the RAN by observing data streams from the CU. The xApp’s role is to correlate anomalies across multiple DUs and enforce network-level mitigation policies through RIC control interfaces. Trained similarly in the O-Cloud, the IDS xApp enables detection of broader or coordinated attacks, offering near-real-time visibility and control at the network layer.

The novelty of our RIDGE architecture lies in its two-layered defense: dApps act as first responders at the DU,

providing rapid, fine-grained edge protection, while xApps deliver situational awareness across multiple nodes by combining aggregated alerts from the dApps with network-level information. Together, they deliver scalable and responsive IDS capabilities tailored to the disaggregated nature of 5G O-RAN deployments. In the next sections, we compare the performances of the dApps and xApps-based IDS using the RIDGE architectural implementation.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND DATA COLLECTION

A. Testbed Setup

To conduct our experiments, we utilized a 5G O-RAN testbed based on the OpenAirInterface (OAI) platform, comprising a Core Network (CN5G), a CU, two DUs, and two Radio Units (O-RUs): the Benetel 5G RAN550 and a B200 Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP). The Benetel is connected to its DU via Split 7.2a, representing a vendor-grade deployment, while the B200 operates under Split 8 for flexible lower-layer experimentation. These DU–RU connections allow us to evaluate performance and security under different functional splits. For edge processing, a high-performance Dell Precision 7920 server is deployed at the network’s edge, co-locating the Near-RT RIC and emulating the O-Cloud edge server—a critical O-RAN vulnerability—while the setup supports the collection of both higher-layer traffic and lower-layer telemetry for the IDS. Figure 2 presents an overview of the testbed and its components.

Fig. 2: The 5G O-RAN testbed setup at UCD Netslab

B. Data Collection

To create the datasets, we launched a variety of scenarios including attacks:

TABLE II: Summary of Captured Datasets, Features, and Descriptions

Dataset	Source	Collection Tool	Features	Description
Higher Layer Network Traffic	CU (Core Network side)	Wireshark + Zeek (conn.log)	<i>src_ip, dst_ip, proto, service, duration, orig_bytes, resp_bytes, conn_state, orig_pkts, resp_pkts, orig_ip_bytes, resp_ip_bytes, history</i>	IP and transport-layer flow metrics extracted per session, capturing connection characteristics and traffic behavior at the CU side.
Lower Layer Radio Telemetry	DU (Distributed Unit side)	Probing to E2 Interface	<i>timestamp, ue_id, cellid, cqi, dlBytes, ulBytes, dlMcs, ulMcs, rsrp, rsrq, rssi, sinr, dlBler, ulBler, pmax, phr, pucch-Snr, puschSnr, ri, pmi, in_sync</i>	UE radio-layer performance and quality indicators during transmission, reflecting PHY and MAC layer conditions observed at the DU side.

CQI: Channel Quality Indicator, **MCS (dl/ul):** Modulation and Coding Scheme index, **RSRP:** Reference Signal Received Power, **RSRQ:** Reference Signal Received Quality, **RSSI:** Received Signal Strength Indicator, **SINR:** Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio, **BLER (dl/ul):** Block Error Rate, **PHR:** Power Headroom Report, **PMI:** Precoding Matrix Indicator, **RI:** Rank Indicator, **in_sync:** UE synchronization status.

- **Benign:** Normal user activity generated by real UEs, including YouTube streaming, file downloads, web browsing, and iPerf traffic.
- **ICMP Flood:** High-volume ICMP Echo Requests from one or two UEs aimed to exhaust control-plane and compute resources.
- **UDP PortScan:** Nmap-based scans probed multiple UDP ports to identify open services without establishing full connections.
- **SYN Flood:** Incomplete TCP handshake requests from single or multiple UEs were used to saturate the server’s connection table.
- **TCP Flood:** High-rate TCP traffic to overwhelm the transport stack and reduce system responsiveness.
- **UDP Flood:** Stateless UDP packets were sent to random ports from one or more UEs to saturate bandwidth and CPU resources.

During each experiment, data were collected simultaneously from the Near-RT RIC and the DU via standardised O-RAN interfaces. At the Near-RT RIC, higher-layer packet data was captured with the packet-capturing xApp, and we used Wireshark and the flow-based aggregation tool Zeek for further analysis. At the DU, E2 interface-based radio telemetry was extracted through link monitoring dApp, including signal quality and UE-specific metrics. This process produced two complementary datasets per attack scenario, enabling direct performance comparison. Table II summarizes details of the two datasets.

C. ML model training

To evaluate the feasibility of deploying lightweight ML models for intrusion detection within the O-RAN architecture, we selected three widely adopted classifiers: Decision Trees (DT), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forests (RF). These models were chosen due to their interpretability, low inference latency, and compatibility with resource-constrained edge environments such as the DU. We used the same model types to evaluate the higher-layer network traffic data for comparison. The DT model was configured with a maximum depth of 10 and a minimum leaf size of 2. The KNN model was evaluated with $k = 5$, using Euclidean distance as the metric. The RF model was trained with 100 estimators and

bootstrap sampling enabled. All models were developed using the Scikit-learn framework in Python, maintaining consistent data processing pipelines across both datasets.

Before training, both datasets were standardized using z-score normalization via `StandardScaler` to ensure consistent feature scaling. Feature selection was performed using correlation analysis, ANOVA F-statistics, and mutual information gain to improve efficiency and reduce complexity. In the radio telemetry dataset, features such as *rsrp*, *sinr*, *dlBler*, *rssi*, and *ri* ranked highly in both ANOVA and mutual information scores, underscoring their relevance in detecting physical-layer anomalies. Each classifier was trained in both binary and multiclass configurations to distinguish between benign and multiple attack types. For model training, the data was split into training and test sets using an 80:20 stratified split. Dataset consists 7237 data records sampled each second for the radio telemetry, while 28 million network flow packets were captured during the same network events. We observe the radio telemetry dataset is much more lightweight, which highlights fewer processing requirements at the DU compared to processing of millions of data records at CU for IDS.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance of dApp-based IDS

We observe that the radio telemetry-based IDS achieves consistently high accuracy in both binary and multiclass classification tasks. In the binary setting, all three models performed exceptionally well, as shown in Table III, with RF reaching 100% accuracy, followed by DT at 99.94% and KNN at 98.39%. This high accuracy is resulting as it is easier for ML models to analyze fewer number of relevant features from the radio telemetry data. In the multiclass classification scenario, the IDS maintained strong performance despite the increased complexity, with RF achieving an accuracy of 99.67%, DT 98.84%, and KNN 92.93%, shown in Table IV. KNN may have lower accuracy than the binary classification as the K is kept consistent to the binary classification, which can result in missing some of the attacks, possibly due to over-smoothing of the decision boundary, specially at UDP scan attacks. However, other ML models provide better and consistent results for all the attack types. Therefore, we

TABLE III: Comparative evaluation of binary ML model performance and efficiency metrics on benchmark IDS and our O-RAN datasets.

Dataset	Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)	Execution Time (s)	CPU Effort (%*s)	Memory Usage (MB)
CIC-IDS2017 [16]	DT	99.88	99.55	99.74	99.65	88.40	357.06	4000.44
	KNN	99.84	99.39	99.65	99.52	359.48	17706.10	4798.47
	RF	99.87	99.57	99.67	99.62	598.45	2360.10	5115.37
NSL-KDD [17]	DT	79.47	96.56	66.30	78.62	0.86	18.17	590.47
	KNN	76.74	92.39	64.44	75.93	2.23	71.37	683.74
	RF	76.63	96.74	61.00	74.82	7.06	25.17	716.54
UNSW-NB15 [18]	DT	99.30	97.29	97.17	97.23	13.04	45.84	7092.75
	KNN	99.08	96.54	96.16	96.35	310.88	15171.34	6879.94
	RF	99.46	98.04	97.67	99.46	207.52	791.16	7174.59
5G-NIDD [10]	DT	98.00	98.39	98.31	98.35	11.85	43.38	9397.66
	KNN	88.10	88.58	92.26	90.38	66.91	3030.89	9558.54
	RF	97.99	98.36	98.31	98.34	126.44	513.31	9637.49
Higher Layer Network Traffic	DT	99.99	99.99	99.99	99.99	0.93	49.66	376.39
	KNN	99.98	99.99	99.99	99.99	13.97	60.46	350.31
	RF	99.99	99.99	99.99	100.00	13.01	121.78	354.68
Lower Layer Radio Telemetry	DT	99.94	99.95	99.94	99.94	0.16	1.06	186.95
	KNN	98.39	98.35	98.38	98.36	0.32	1.23	187.39
	RF	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.70	4.53	185.90

show that DU-based radio telemetry can provide significantly accurate IDS inference for different ML implementations across multiple attack types. It highlights that IDS models can achieve higher accuracy by using a smaller set of relevant features rather than relying on many upper-layer features that may not add value for threat prediction.

B. Performance Comparison of dApps vs xApps-based IDS

We then compared the performance of the dApp at the DU compared to the xApp IDS developed from the same attack scenarios (Table III). Both demonstrate a near 100% detection rate for the datasets. However, the advantage of using dApp is further illustrated by the computational overhead, where the dApps trained with radio telemetry consume significantly fewer resources. The execution time to analyze the batch of test data is much smaller with near real-time performance with only milliseconds range at the DU with the dApp-based IDS. Moreover, the CPU effort is much less, with only maximum total of 4.53% execution requirement with RF, while higher layer requires 121.78% for the similar RF model. The memory usage for the dApp is only around 50% of the total memory requirement of the xApp. These behaviors can be expected as relatively smaller models are sufficient to train smaller number of important features from radio telemetry than the bulky models resulting from large number of features at higher layer network traffic. Thus, we clearly observe the radio telemetry dApp-based IDS provides much lightweight execution with a similar accuracy in detecting intrusions to the xApps [7].

C. Evaluating IDS Against Benchmark Datasets

To further validate our results, we compared our models against standard IDS datasets: CIC-IDS2017 [16], UNSW-NB15 [18], NSL-KDD [17], and 5G-NIDD dataset [10]. A fair comparison was ensured by applying uniform preprocessing, feature extraction, and default model hyperparameters across all datasets. As shown in Table III, high detection performance was achieved on CIC-IDS2017, UNSW-NB15, and 5G-NIDD across all models, with accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores consistently exceeding 96%. NSL-KDD exhibited the lowest performance among the evaluated datasets, particularly

with the RF model, where recall and F1 scores were notably lower. This suggests that while NSL-KDD remains a popular benchmark, its data characteristics pose challenges for maintaining high detection rates, particularly on complex attacks.

Our dApp- and xApp-based IDS models match the performance of the benchmark datasets while significantly reducing execution time, CPU usage, and memory consumption. The dApp-based IDS, leveraging radio telemetry, offers the best balance of accuracy and efficiency by detecting anomalies at the physical layer without the overhead of packet inspection, making it ideal for resource-constrained O-RAN DUs.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This research demonstrated the feasibility of deploying an efficient, DU-centric intrusion detection system by leveraging radio telemetry features exposed via the E2 interface in the O-RAN architecture. Our proposed dApp-based solution achieved competitive detection accuracy compared to conventional xApp-based IDS implementations, while significantly reducing execution time, CPU usage, and memory consumption. These results highlight the practicality and promise of deploying lightweight dApps for security monitoring tasks directly at the network edge. Future work will focus on applying more advanced ML models to address complex threats, such as those featured in our expanded public dataset [19], [20]. We will investigate techniques like model quantization and pruning to deploy efficient deep learning models at the DU, and explore decentralized paradigms like Federated Learning to enable collaborative threat detection across the radio edge.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Polese, M. Dohler, F. Dressler, M. Erol-Kantarci, R. Jana, R. Knopp, and T. Melodia, "Empowering the 6g cellular architecture with open ran," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, 2023.
- [2] C. Fiandrino, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, M. Polese, T. Melodia, and J. Widmer, "Explora: Ai/ml explainability for the open ran," *Proceedings of the ACM on Networking*, vol. 1, no. CoNEXT3, pp. 1–26, 2023.
- [3] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, S. Basagni, and T. Melodia, "Colo-ran: Developing machine learning-based xapps for open ran closed-loop control on programmable experimental platforms," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 5787–5800, 2022.
- [4] T. Tsourdinis, N. Makris, T. Korakis, and S. Fdida, "Ai-driven network intrusion detection and resource allocation in real-world o-ran 5g networks," in *Proceedings of the 30th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, pp. 1842–1849, 2024.

TABLE IV: Comparative evaluation of multiclass ML model performance across attack types on the 5G-NIDD and our O-RAN datasets

Dataset	Model	Metric	SYN Flood	UDP Flood	ICMP Flood	UDP Scan	Benign	Overall Accuracy	Exec Time (s)	CPU (%*s)	Memory (MB)
5G-NIDD	DT	Accuracy	100.00	98.00	100.00	100.00	98.00	97.92	8.60	49.92	3130.39
		Precision	99.95	97.41	100.00	99.94	97.40				
		Recall	99.95	97.27	100.00	99.84	97.53				
		F1-Score	99.95	97.34	100.00	99.89	97.47				
	KNN	Accuracy	99.10	88.73	99.93	99.16	88.05	82.66	67.95	3154.08	3050.29
		Precision	15.41	83.22	69.42	66.95	86.97				
		Recall	2.96	87.67	38.53	71.81	81.96				
		F1-Score	4.96	85.39	49.56	69.29	84.39				
	RF	Accuracy	100.00	97.98	100.00	100.00	97.98	97.93	138.03	589.32	2965.42
		Precision	100.00	97.36	100.00	99.97	97.41				
		Recall	100.00	97.28	100.00	99.81	97.49				
		F1-Score	100.00	97.32	100.00	99.89	97.45				
Higher Layer Network Traffic	DT	Accuracy	99.99	96.29	95.92	99.99	99.62	95.92	7.88	80.57	719.27
		Precision	100.00	99.99	80.33	100.00	99.97				
		Recall	99.98	77.70	100.00	100.00	97.81				
		F1-Score	99.99	87.45	89.09	80.00	98.18				
	KNN	Accuracy	99.99	96.28	95.90	99.99	99.59	95.88	120.43	622.23	762.60
		Precision	99.99	99.94	80.51	100.00	99.33				
		Recall	99.98	77.67	99.41	99.97	98.21				
		F1-Score	85.45	87.41	88.97	99.98	98.76				
	RF	Accuracy	99.99	96.29	95.92	100	99.63	95.92	39.46	308.61	747.40
		Precision	100.00	100.00	80.33	100.00	99.98				
		Recall	99.98	77.70	100.00	100.00	97.81				
		F1-Score	99.99	87.45	89.09	100.00	98.88				
Lower Layer Radio Telemetry	DT	Accuracy	99.55	99.44	99.33	100	99.94	98.84	0.21	4.54	186.12
		Precision	97.67	98.78	96.54	100.00	100.00				
		Recall	98.59	98.18	98.24	100.00	99.87				
		F1-Score	98.13	98.48	97.38	100.00	99.93				
	KNN	Accuracy	96.57	96.68	96.68	99.83	98.45	92.93	0.36	1.66	179.83
		Precision	85.45	91.16	87.78	100.00	97.93				
		Recall	85.45	90.61	85.46	66.67	98.44				
		F1-Score	85.45	90.88	86.61	80.00	98.18				
	RF	Accuracy	99.88	99.77	99.77	100	100	99.67	1.02	21.67	181.99
		Precision	99.53	99.70	98.27	100.00	100.00				
		Recall	99.53	99.09	100.00	100.00	100.00				
		F1-Score	99.53	99.39	99.13	100.00	100.00				

- [5] J. Groen, S. D’Oro, U. Demir, L. Bonati, M. Polese, T. Melodia, and K. Chowdhury, “Implementing and evaluating security in o-ran: Interfaces, intelligence, and platforms,” *IEEE Network*, 2025.
- [6] E. N. Amachaghi, M. Shojafar, C. H. Foh, and K. Moessner, “A survey for intrusion detection systems in open ran,” *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [7] S. D’Oro, M. Polese, L. Bonati, H. Cheng, and T. Melodia, “dapps: Distributed applications for real-time inference and control in o-ran,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 11, pp. 52–58, 2022.
- [8] P. Waghmode, M. Kanumuri, H. El-Ocla, and T. Boyle, “Intrusion detection system based on machine learning using least square support vector machine,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 12066, 2025.
- [9] A. S. Ahanger, S. M. Khan, F. Masoodi, and A. O. Salau, “Advanced intrusion detection in internet of things using graph attention networks,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 9831, 2025.
- [10] S. Samarakoon, Y. Siriwardhana, P. Porabage, M. Liyanage, S.-Y. Chang, J. Kim, J. Kim, and M. Ylianttila, “5g-nidd: A comprehensive network intrusion detection dataset generated over 5g wireless network,” 2022.
- [11] Y. Siriwardhana, S. Samarakoon, P. Porabage, M. Liyanage, S.-Y. Chang, J. Kim, J. Kim, and M. Ylianttila, “Descriptor: 5g wireless network intrusion detection dataset (5g-nidd),” *IEEE Data Descriptions*, pp. 1–12, 2025.
- [12] M. A. Hossain and M. S. Islam, “Ensuring network security with a robust intrusion detection system using ensemble-based machine learning,” *Array*, vol. 19, p. 100306, 2023.
- [13] H. Wen, P. Porras, V. Yegneswaran, A. Gehani, and Z. Lin, “5g-spectator: An o-ran compliant layer-3 cellular attack detection service,” in *Proceedings of the 31st Annual Network and Distributed System Security Symposium, NDSS*, vol. 24, 2024.
- [14] A. S. Abdalla, J. Moore, N. Adhikari, and V. Marojevic, “Ztran: Prototyping zero trust security xapps for open radio access network deployments,” *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 2024.
- [15] A. Lacava, L. Bonati, N. Mohamadi, R. Gangula, F. Kaltenberger, P. Johari, S. D’Oro, F. Cuomo, M. Polese, and T. Melodia, “dapps: Enabling real-time ai-based open ran control,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.16502*, 2025.
- [16] I. Sharafaldin, A. H. Lashkari, A. A. Ghorbani, et al., “Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization,” *ICISSp*, vol. 1, no. 2018, pp. 108–116, 2018.
- [17] M. Tavallae, E. Bagheri, W. Lu, and A. A. Ghorbani, “A detailed analysis of the kdd cup 99 data set,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence for Security and Defense Applications (CISDA)*, (Ottawa, ON, Canada), pp. 1–6, 2009.
- [18] N. Moustafa and J. Slay, “Unsw-nb15: a comprehensive data set for network intrusion detection systems (unsw-nb15 network data set),” in *2015 Military Communications and Information Systems Conference (MilCIS)*, pp. 1–6, 2015.
- [19] U. NetsLab, “Netslab 5g o-ran intrusion detection dataset (5g o-ran idd).” <https://netslab.ucd.ie/netslab-datasets/netslab-5goran-idd/>.
- [20] F. Abed Zadeh, A. Coviciss, V. Ravihansa, C. Sandeepa, and M. Liyanage, “Descriptor of the 5g open radio access network multi-modal intrusion detection dataset (NetsLab-5G-O-RAN-IDD),” *TechRxiv*, 2025.